

HUMAN RESOURCES MANAGEMENT PRACTICES IN NIGERIAN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN RELATION TO HRM PRINCIPLES: A CRITICAL APPRAISAL

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Abstract

The necessary homage has not been paid to human resources management in Nigerian public secondary schools. Hence, this study critically appraised human resources management (HRM) procedures in Nigerian public secondary schools, particularly how well they adhere to accepted HRM principles. This paper described human resources management as the effective management and development of employees toward achieving the goals of an organization. The paper explored applying strategic human resources management principles to enhance workforce productivity, organizational effectiveness, and student outcomes. The components of human resources management were explained as strategic human resources planning, recruitment and selection process, staff development, compensation and benefit, and performance evaluation to mention but a few. Challenges of human resources management were examined as inadequate funding, shortage of qualified teachers, poor compensation and motivation, inadequate staff development, and brain drain among others. The paper suggested among other things, that increased funding, strengthening teacher recruitment and retention strategies, enhancing compensation and benefits, and investing in professional development will move the educational sector forward and foster a conducive and progressive working environment for all employees.

Keywords: Human Resources Management, Secondary schools, Principles, Practices.

Introduction

One essential component of any organization's efficacy and long-term sustainability is human resources management (HRM). Educational institutions are not excluded. HRM strategies are critical to developing a productive workforce, raising teacher

effectiveness, and achieving better overall educational outcomes in public secondary schools in Nigeria (Akanbi & Ajibola, 2021). However, recent studies have shown that Contemporary HRM practices in Nigerian public secondary schools differ significantly from accepted HRM principles. These institutions' inability to

manage their human resources effectively is still hampered by problems like ineffective hiring procedures, little opportunity for professional growth, subpar performance management systems, and low staff engagement (Ezeokoli & Udegbonam, 2022).

It is impossible to overestimate the effect that inadequate HRM procedures have on Nigeria's educational system particularly secondary education. According to Adetunji & Osakwe, 2023, ineffective HRM procedures result in low job satisfaction, high employee turnover, and a drop in teacher morale, all of which hurt the educational experiences and achievements of students. A comprehensive evaluation of these procedures is therefore urgently required to bring them into compliance with global HRM standards that prioritise capacity building, employee engagement, and strategic planning (Obasi & Nwankwo, 2020).

Public secondary schools in Nigeria confront more difficulties as a result of the lack of alignment with these principles, which frequently leads to a disorganised approach to managing school personnel (Okoro & Anozie, 2024). In light of these challenges, a critical examination of HRM practices in the Nigerian educational system is necessary to identify areas of improvement. By aligning HRM practices with established principles, educational institutions can create a more productive, motivated, and engaged workforce. Addressing these issues will ultimately contribute to the overall development and improvement of the educational system in Nigeria. This paper therefore aimed to identify gaps and obstacles in the HRM practices used in Nigerian public secondary schools by critically examining them in light of accepted HRM principles, and also give recommendations that can foster positive changes in HRM practices and enhance the quality of education and

organizational effectiveness in the Nigerian secondary educational system.

Human Resources Management in Education

Human Resources Management (HRM) plays a fundamental role in determining the efficiency and effectiveness of any organization, including educational institutions. HRM involves the effective management and development of employees toward achieving the goals of an organization. Human resources management has also been defined as the process of managing employees in a way that maximizes their potential and contributes positively to the overall goals of the organization. Piwowar-Sulej (2021). Human Resources Management is mainly concerned with the acquisition, maintenance, development, utilization, and coordination of people at work to get the best from them. Organizational performance depends heavily on the efficiency of human resources working in the organization. Therefore, all essential aspects of human resources management ranging from planning, recruitment, selection, motivation, training and development, performance appraisal, compensation management and industrial relations should be properly designed. Human Resources Management is everything about employees. (Anwar & Abdullah 2021).

Alsafadi and Altaht, (2021) opined that HRM principles encompass a wide array of strategic and operational approaches aimed at optimizing the potential of an organization's workforce. These principles include the principle of scientific selection, the principle of individual training and development, the principle of free flow of communication, the principle of participation, the principle of fair remuneration, the principle of incentive, the principle of dignity of labor,

the principle of labour-management cooperation, the principle of team spirit and principle of contribution to national prosperity. A well-implemented HRM framework ensures that the right talent is attracted, recruited, nurtured, and retained, contributing to enhanced employee satisfaction and organizational success.

The concept of Human Resource Management (HRM) in education focuses on the application of HRM principles and practices to the unique context of educational institutions. It involves the strategic management of the workforce comprising teachers, administrators, support staff, and other personnel involved in the education process to create an environment that fosters academic excellence, supports student success, and promotes the professional growth and well-being of educators and staff (Qutni, et.al 2021).

HRM in education centers on the harmonization of the activities and efforts of the staff in educational settings so that educational goals are achieved. In other words, it means utilizing people to perform duties and functions in the schools. HRM in school involves forecasting the staff needs, attracting the right caliber of teachers, recruiting them, retaining them, developing them, compensating them, supporting them, and evaluating them. It involves the process of motivating teachers and other workers within the school system to maximize their performance to obtain maximum output from them starting from the day they were recruited. (Danburam & Umar 2022).

Fundamental practices of HRM in education include; Strategic HR planning, Talent Acquisition, Professional Development, Performance Evaluation, Teacher Compensation and Benefits, Employee Engagement, Teacher Retention, Classroom Management Support, Student-Teacher Ratio, Education Policy Compliance, Educational Leadership

Development, Parent and Community Engagement etc.

Components of Human Resources Management in Nigerian Educational System Concerning Human Resources Management Principles

The practices of Human Resource Management in an educational system encompass various aspects related to managing the workforce in the school system and aligning HR strategies with school goals and objectives. Even though HRM is being practiced in schools in Nigeria, the so-called practice is filled with various issues and challenges thereby causing more harm than good in the system. The following are the manifestations of HRM practices in the Nigerian educational system as they relate to HRM principles.

- 1. Strategic HR Planning:** Strategic HR planning involves projecting future staffing needs and developing plans to meet these requests. Strategic HR planning helps educational institutions address talent shortages, identify critical staffing needs, and align HR strategies with the institution's long-term objectives (Olatokun & Akinfolarin, 2019). In the context of the Nigerian education system, one of the major challenges in HRM that make strategic planning difficult to achieve is the issue of inadequate funding. Despite government promises to allocate 26% of its annual budget to education, this has not been achieved, with the sector receiving less than 10% in recent years (UNESCO, 2021). Nigerian educational institutions often struggle to secure sufficient financial resources to carry out strategic planning, this has resulted in inadequate human and material resources, inadequate facilities, lack

of competitive salaries and benefits, making it difficult to attract and retain highly skilled professionals. One other significant challenge faced by HRM in Nigerian schools as a result of poor funding is the shortage of qualified teachers. This shortage is particularly prevalent in remote areas, where attracting and retaining qualified educators is difficult. The lack of qualified teachers negatively affects the quality of education and student outcomes as HRM manages to retain and maintain qualified teachers. Also, insufficient funding negates many HRM principles, especially the principle of strategic planning, which requires aligning HR strategies with organizational goals and talent acquisition and retention.

2. Recruitment, Selection and Placement: Effective talent acquisition and retention are essential HRM practices responsible for attracting and retaining qualified and dedicated educators and staff. Looking at the Nigerian educational system, oftentimes, recruitment and selection of teachers are done not on merit, but rather based on whom you know. This has caused great damage to the system of education as the life of future leaders is entrusted in the hands of substandard teachers. The question is, what becomes of this country in the next ten years? Strategic recruitment efforts and competitive compensation packages can help retain the best talent in schools (Awojobi & Egbetokun, 2018). Also, teachers' placement constitutes another hindrance in the selection process of teachers in

secondary schools. Often in Nigeria, teachers are unfairly dispersed and this is always injurious to schools, especially the rural ones. Due to political intrusion, many teachers are made to teach subjects with which they are unacquainted, which is unfair to both teachers and students. It contributes to teacher stress and less-than-optimal learning outcomes for students. This is most apparent in subjects where trained teachers are scarce, especially in mathematics, English, and sciences. This has rendered so many teachers incompetent because they are square pegs in round holes and this has been a threat to teachers' selection process in secondary schools in Osun State (Ibrahim & Adebayo, 2023).

3. Performance Evaluation: HRM in education implements fair and transparent performance evaluation systems to assess educators' teaching effectiveness, administrative efficiency, and overall contributions to the institution. In Nigerian schools, teachers are not well assessed. The Kaduna State teachers' competency test organized by the Kaduna State government in 2017 was a good example of the deteriorating state of teacher quality in Nigerian public schools. About two-thirds of primary school teachers failed to score up to seventy-five percent when asked to write examinations meant for primary four pupils in Kaduna state. If similar exercises were to be conducted in other states of the federation, many teachers would fall victim and probably be dealt with for incompetency and lack of necessary basic knowledge.

The purpose of performance appraisal is to recognize good performance and reward it, and to provide constructive criticism for lapses in performance. In Nigeria, aside from the number of years of service, secondary school teachers are to be assessed through the Annual Performance Evaluation Report (APER) before they are promoted. In some states, little or no emphasis has been given to APER for teachers' promotion. Some principals only tick the form as they like with little or no consideration for teachers' real efforts. This is against the principle of performance appraisal.

- 4. Staff Development:** Employee development is crucial for enhancing the skills and knowledge of educators and staff. Continuous training and professional development programs can improve educator performance and student learning outcomes in the Nigerian education system (Okoh & Okoh, 2017). However, this vital principle is not given well-deserved attention in the system of education in this country. Some teachers in Nigerian schools ever since their employment have not been sent on any professional development programme that will enhance their professionalism. Oftentimes, school heads use favoritism and nepotism in selecting their favorite teachers to attend conferences or 2seminar because of the meager allowance attached to some training. For the past ten years in Osun State, TESCOM has not organized any tangible staff development programme for senior school teaching staff. For the Basic Schools, SUBEB does organize a

cluster meeting in the form of a workshop once in three years. The worst aspect of it is that, even when workshops or seminars are organized, teachers tend to restrict change and prefer to remain status quo which is a setback to the growth of the individual, as well as that of the school as a whole and also contradict the HRM principle of individual/organizational development.

- 5. Compensation and Benefits:** Fair and competitive compensation and benefits are vital for motivating and retaining skilled educators and staff. Adequate compensation can improve job satisfaction and foster a positive work culture within educational institutions (Sani & Aliero, 2021). However, teachers in Nigerian schools are underpaid, often they are denied promotion as and when due, and school environments are not conducive. For instance, primary school teachers in Osun State receive #30,000. For goodness's sake, what can this amount do in the current economic situation of the country? Another significant challenge under compensation in HRM is brain drain. Nigerian educational institutions find it challenging to retain talented and experienced educators due to the lure of better opportunities abroad. TETFund Executive Secretary recently lamented over 137 scholars sponsored abroad by TETFund and refused to return to Nigeria. This brain drain adversely affects the quality of education in Nigeria. Ogunyemi (2019), posited that a lack of incentives and unfavorable working conditions contribute to the increasing migration of skilled

professionals to other countries. Therefore, every organisation needs to give compensation to its workforce a priority. In the like terms, Adegelu (2021) stated that in some government-owned institutions in Nigeria, lecturers have not been well-compensated. This has caused intermittent strikes of different forms which could affect realisation of the stated goals of these institutions. All these, and the like are against the principle and good practices of HRM as regards compensation and benefits.

6. **Principle of Diversity and Inclusion:** Effective HRM practices should carry all members of the organization along in all its activities. Promoting diversity and inclusion is crucial for Nigerian educational institutions, given the diverse cultural and ethnic backgrounds of students and staff. Embracing diversity can enrich the learning experience and promote cultural sensitivity (Sani & Aliero, 2021).
7. **Principle of Compliance with Labor Laws and Educational Policies:** Adherence to labour laws and educational policies is vital to ensure ethical practices and legal compliance within educational institutions (Iyoha & Abraham, 2017). Ensuring adherence to education laws, regulations, and policies would generate and maintain ethical standards and also provide a safe and inclusive learning environment.

Challenges facing Human Resources Management in Nigerian Secondary Schools

The challenges of HRM in Nigeria's educational system are numerous, and they vary based on different factors such as the location of the institution, the size of the organization, and the level of government involvement. Some of the key challenges include:

1. Inadequate Funding: The Nigerian educational system is plagued by inadequate funding which affects the ability of HRM to operate effectively. Budgetary constraints limit human resource managers' ability to recruit, retain and develop high-quality educators. As a result, institutions struggle to attract and retain highly qualified teachers. (Solaja & Odulaja, 2014). In addition to this, the rapid population growth and increased demand for education have exerted immense pressure on institutions to recruit and retain qualified teaching and administrative staff. The recruitment process may not always adhere to standardized principles, leading to the hiring of underqualified personnel or neglecting the importance of diversity and inclusion. According to Adeyemi (2017), insufficient funding contradicts the principle of strategic planning, which requires aligning HR strategies with organizational goals and consequently leads to a lack of competitive salaries and benefits, making it difficult to attract and retain highly skilled professionals.

2. Shortage of Qualified Teachers: One of the significant challenges faced by HRM in Nigerian schools is the shortage of qualified teachers which is totally against the principle of talent acquisition and retention. This shortage is particularly prevalent in remote areas, where attracting and retaining qualified educators is difficult. The lack of qualified teachers negatively affects the quality of education and student outcomes and also negates the principle of talent acquisition and retention

as HRM manages to retain and maintain qualified teachers (Jacob & et.al, 2020).

3. Inadequate Compensation: Katete and Nyangarika (2020) identified another challenge in HRM as the issue of inadequate compensation for teachers and staff. In the Nigerian secondary educational system, there have been instances of inadequate remuneration, delayed salary payments, and limited non-monetary benefits, which can contribute to dissatisfaction and high turnover rates. A good example is the case of Osun teachers during the regime of Governor Aregbesola in Osun State when teachers were being paid half their salary for years. Imagine the quality of education those teachers would deliver to students. Inadequate compensation also hampers the recruitment of highly qualified individuals to the education sector. This contradicts the principle of employee relations, which emphasizes creating a positive work environment to enhance employee motivation and job satisfaction. Azikiwe, (2014) asserted that poor working conditions coupled with low pay rates, make it difficult to attract and retain the best talent in Nigeria's educational sector. An unattractive work environment for educators discourages passionate and progressive people from seeking a career in the education sector.

4. Brain Drain: Another significant challenge in HRM is brain drain. Nigerian educational institutions find it challenging to retain talented and experienced educators due to the lure of better opportunities abroad. This brain drain adversely affects the quality of education in Nigeria. According to Ogunyemi (2019), the lack of incentives and unfavorable working conditions contribute to the increasing migration of skilled professionals to other countries.

5. Inadequate Training and Development: The lack of sufficient training and development opportunities is a prevalent challenge in HRM within the Nigerian education system. Teachers and administrators often do not have access to continuous professional development programs, hindering their ability to adapt to changing educational practices (Onu, Akinlabi & Fakunmoju, 2014). A study by Ogunsaju (2020) highlights the need for comprehensive training programs to enhance the skills and knowledge of educators. Inadequate training and development go against the principle of individual and organizational development.

6. Problem of Diversity and Inclusion: Diversity and inclusion are a significant concern in HRM within the Nigerian education system. Ethnic and cultural diversity among students and staff may not always be effectively addressed (Sani & Aliero, 2021).

7. Non-compliance with Labour Laws and Educational Policies: The laws and policies are vital for educational institutions' sustainability and ethical practices. Inconsistent implementation of HR policies and non-compliance with labor laws and regulations may pose challenges for HRM practices. This is totally against the principle of legal and ethical HRM practices.

Way Forward to HRM Challenges in the Education System in Nigeria

1. **Increased Funding:** Adequate funding is crucial to address HRM challenges in the Nigerian education system. The Nigerian government should allocate a higher percentage of the national budget to education and prioritize adequate funding for staff salaries, benefits, and professional development. Adeyemi (2017) suggests that

increased funding will attract and retain highly skilled professionals, improving the quality of education.

2. **Strengthening Teacher Recruitment and Retention Strategies:** To address the shortage of qualified teachers, HRM in the education system should develop robust recruitment and retention strategies. This can include offering competitive salaries and benefits, providing housing and transportation allowances, and creating conducive work environments that promote job satisfaction.
3. **Enhancing Compensation and Benefits:** Implementing transparent and fair compensation structures, adhering to salary payment schedules, and offering additional benefits like health insurance and retirement plans can improve employee morale and retention in schools, and boost the overall quality of education in Nigeria.
4. **Incentives and Retention Strategies:** To mitigate brain drain, it is essential to implement effective incentives and retention strategies. Nigerian educational institutions should offer competitive salaries, benefits, and opportunities for career growth. Ogunyemi (2019) proposes the establishment of favorable working conditions and the provision of attractive incentives to encourage skilled professionals to remain in Nigeria.
5. **Investing in Professional Development:** HRM should prioritize investing in professional development opportunities for teachers and staff. This can be

achieved by allocating funds for training programs, organizing workshops and conferences, and promoting collaboration and knowledge sharing among educators. By enhancing professional development opportunities, HRM can ensure continuous improvement in teaching practices and educational outcomes. Ogunsaju (2020) recommends the establishment of a comprehensive training framework that promotes lifelong learning and enhances the capabilities of educators.

6. **Diversity and Inclusion:** Educational institutions in Nigeria should embrace diversity and inclusion as core values. HRM practices should promote equity and ensure equal opportunities for all students, teachers, and staff, regardless of their cultural and ethnic backgrounds (Sani & Aliero, 2021).
7. **Compliance with Labour Laws and Educational Policies:** Adhering to labour laws and educational policies is critical for ethical and legal compliance. Educational institutions should establish HR policies that align with relevant regulations, conduct regular audits, and provide training to HR personnel and staff on legal and ethical standards (Awojobi & Egbetokun, 2018).

Conclusion

HRM plays a crucial role in the Nigerian educational system by managing human resources effectively and efficiently. The paper critically examined the Human Resources Management practices in the Nigerian educational

system in line with the principles of Human Resources Management. It highlighted the challenges of HRM in the Nigerian educational system including; poor funding, inadequate salary structure, lack of training and development, problems of diversity and inclusion, and non-compliance with labor law and educational policies among others. The paper further suggested that abiding by the HRM principles such as maintaining a fair and equal work environment, providing appropriate compensation and benefits, and promoting professional development can improve job satisfaction and organizational effectiveness. Educational institutions need to implement HRM practices to attract and retain talented educators, which ultimately leads to providing better quality education and student outcomes. Therefore, the management of human resources in the Nigerian education sector must be given high priority to ensure the growth and development of the system.

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